

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXXII. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF XANTHONES

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Polyphosphoric acid has been found to be an efficient condensing agent for the synthesis of xanthenes from *o*-hydroxycarboxylic acid and polyhydric phenols. Good yields of xanthenes have been obtained from resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol, α - and β -naphthols by condensing them with salicylic acid in presence of polyphosphoric acid.

Xanthenes and their derivatives have been prepared from *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid or their substitution products and monohydric, dihydric and trihydric phenols by heating their mixtures in acetic anhydride (Kostanecki *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1894, 3981; 1892, 25, 1640, 1648, 1654; 1893, 26, 71; 1894, 27, 1989). The Nencki reaction (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1881, 23, 147) was applied by Michael (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1883, 5, 81) to the preparation of xanthenes from resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol and salicylic acid. Seshadri and Pankjmani (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 396) have applied the Nencki reaction to obtain xanthenes from resorcinol and its methyl ether, using salicylic acid. Shah *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3982; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 28, 75) have used a mixture of anhydrous zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride for the synthesis of xanthenes and their derivatives by condensing mono- and poly-hydroxybenzoic acids with polyhydric phenols. This condensing agent has been found to be superior to zinc chloride. The Friedel-Crafts reaction has been applied by Seshadri and Venkatrao (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 37A 710) for obtaining xanthenes from salicyl chloride and trimethyl ethers of phloroglucinol and pyrogallol.

In the present case we have found that polyphosphoric acid acts as a very efficient condensing agent for the preparation of xanthenes from a mixture of salicylic acid and phenols. We have condensed salicylic acid with resorcinol, orcinol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol and phloroglucinol and have obtained the xanthenes in good yields. These xanthenes were identified by comparing their mixed m.p. and other properties with those of the authentic specimens, prepared by the known methods. These products are free from the colouring matters and resinous products formed when either zinc chloride or its mixture with phosphorus oxychloride is used. The yield of 1-hydroxyxanthone is nearly 20% and that of 3-hydroxyxanthone, very poor when zinc chloride is used. Polyphosphoric acid, however, affords a mixture of 1-hydroxyxanthone (45%) and 3-hydroxyxanthone (5%). Thus, this method is fairly general, and we are engaged in applying it to other *o*-hydroxycarboxylic acids and polyhydroxy compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Polyphosphoric acid was prepared from syrupy orthophosphoric acid and P_2O_5 by the method of Sukh Dev (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 262).

1-Hydroxyxanthone and 3-Hydroxyxanthone.—A mixture of salicylic acid (6 g.), resorcinol (6 g.) and polyphosphoric acid (25 c.c. orthophosphoric acid and 40 g. P_2O_5) was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured over crushed ice. The solid was repeatedly washed with hot water to remove the unchanged components and the residue was treated with a 5% sodium carbonate solution. The insoluble residue was treated with a 10% NaOH solution to obtain the sodium salt of 1-hydroxyxanthone. It was then boiled with HCl (dil.), the solid was filtered and crystallised from alcohol in yellow-orange needles, m.p. 148° , yield 5.6 g. Its alcoholic solution developed with ferric chloride a brown coloration, changing to green (Michael, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 149°).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethyl acetate in needles, m.p. 170° (Michael, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 166°).

The solid, obtained by the acidification of the sodium carbonate extract, was crystallised from acetone in thick yellow needles, m.p. 238° , yield 600 mg. Kostanecki *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. $240-41^\circ$ for 3-hydroxyxanthone. Its solutions in H_2SO_4 (conc.) and alkali are markedly fluorescent

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from absolute alcohol in needles, m.p. 160° (Kostanecki *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 161°).

1-Hydroxy-3-methylxanthone was prepared by heating a mixture of salicylic acid (6 g.), orcinol (6 g.) and P.P.A. (64 g.). The solid isolated in the usual manner was crystallised from dilute alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 148° (Michael, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 148°), yield 3.6 g. Its alcoholic solution developed a greenish coloration with ferric chloride.

1:3-Dihydroxyxanthone was prepared from salicylic acid (6 g.), phloroglucinol (6 g.) and P.P.A. (64 g.). The product, isolated in the usual manner, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine white needles, m.p. 256° (Robinson and Nishikawa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 859, report m.p. $256-58^\circ$), yield 5 g. Its alcoholic solution developed a green colour with ferric chloride.

The *diacetate* was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 147° (Rao and Seshadri, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 145°).

3:4-*Benzoxanthone*, prepared from salicylic acid (6 g.), α -naphthol (6 g.) and P.P.A. (64 g.), was crystallised from absolute alcohol in tiny needles, m.p. 155° (Kostanecki *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 155°), yield 1.0 g. Its alcoholic solution developed a green colour with ferric chloride. It showed fluorescence in H₂SO₄ (conc.) solution.

2:3-*Benzoxanthone*, prepared from salicylic acid (6 g.), β -naphthol (6 g.) and P.P.A. (64 g.), was crystallised from dilute alcohol in microcrystalline plates, m.p. 138-40° (Kostanecki *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 140°), yield 1.1 g.

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